

BALANCING CONFLICTING INTERESTS DURING PREGNANCY:

ULTRASOUND v. REALITY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines whether it is morally correct and legally possible to police a pregnant woman's behaviour in order to protect the foetus. The first part of the paper discusses whether a pregnant woman should be forced to have a caesarean section; it proposes a 'modified competency test' which begins with the rebuttable presumption that the competent woman can refuse the operation if she offers at least one reason for her decision. The second part of the paper asks what should be the law's reaction in cases where the pregnant addict causes serious injury or death to the foetus. There can be a criminal prosecution, civil liability or taking the baby from the mother as soon as she gives birth. Finally, a 'middle solution' is proposed which encourages women to come forward so that they can be rehabilitated. In both debates the pregnant woman should be the one who decides about her own future and society should only have a residual role; only this method will adequately protect both the mother's and the foetus' interests.

A INTRODUCTION

The patient's right to control her body is so well established, at least in theory, that it has almost become a mantra. If a paranoid, schizophrenic man can decide whether he wants his leg amputated or not¹ then all competent people have the right to decide whether anyone can touch their body, no matter the consequences. This is both legally and morally correct; however, does the same principle apply to pregnant women? In particular, should a pregnant woman be able to deny a life-saving (for her and her foetus) caesarean section? The law on the importance of patient autonomy seems settled; but as Lord Mustill stated in *AG's Reference (No.3 of 1994)*,² '[t]he relationship was one of bond, not identity.'³ The mother and the foetus were two distinct organisms living symbiotically, not a single organism with two aspects. The mother's leg was part of the mother; the foetus was not. Clearly, autonomy is not the only consideration to be taken into account in these circumstances.

The debate largely rests on whether a pregnant woman is the only person who can decide what happens to her body or whether society, in the voice of the doctor or the judge, has a say as well. The question is a difficult one: on one hand, pregnant women should not be treated differently than anyone else. They make sacrifices for the foetus they carry inside them that no one knows of. If they are not willing to make this ultimate sacrifice, that is their right and they should not be morally blamed or legally punished. On the other hand, they consented to the risks of pregnancy, including a caesarean section when they decided not to have an abortion, thus establishing a moral obligation towards the foetus.

However, the question of a forced caesarean section cannot be seen in isolation from other maternity questions. If society has the right to trespass the woman's right of autonomy and self-determination during the delivery of the child, then it arguably has the right to impose some limits on what she can do during the gestation period as well. This raises another series of difficult issues: even though it is easy to say that a woman should not be

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¹ *Re C* [1994] 1 All ER 819.

² [1998] AC 245.

³ *ibid* 255.

using heroin while pregnant, it is more difficult to consider an addicted woman who has been turned down by the rehabilitation centre due to limited resources as morally culpable. Moreover, if we decide that such behaviour is both immoral towards the foetus and society's values, is it also worth punishing? If our aim is to punish the woman for failing to meet society's standards, then post-delivery punishment might be legitimate; but if we are trying to protect the foetus, punishment is simply unproductive, unless we accept that it could potentially have a deterrent effect to future pregnant women. The first part of this essay will deal with forced caesarean section and the second part with society's right to interfere during the nine-month gestation period.

B THE CAESAREAN SECTION DEBATE

1 The Pregnant Woman's Self-Determination

Following the case of *St George's NHS Trust v S*,⁴ the law finally seems settled: everyone, including a woman carrying a viable foetus, has the right to decide how her body is treated. If that compromises hers and her baby's life, it is an acceptable price to be paid for ensuring the patient's autonomy. As it was stated in *Re MB (An Adult: Medical Treatment)* 'the mother may indeed later regret the outcome, but the alternative would be an unwanted invasion of the right of the woman to make a decision.'⁵ There is no certain definition of autonomy; all we can say is that it encompasses the right to determine by ourselves what we want to happen to something as intimate as our body. In Sperling's words, the pregnant woman scenario is the 'test case for the protection of the woman's right of self-determination in the eyes of the law.'⁶ Even in the developed world, one in every 10,000 women dies as a result of a caesarean section.⁷ 20-45% of women who go through a caesarean section have an operation-associated infection while the chances of suffering from pulmonary embolism and dying are nine times higher than with normal vaginal delivery.⁸ If a woman is not allowed to decide whether to go through such risks, then the whole concept of autonomy must be unreal.

These statistics suggest that caesarean section is a risky operation; yet, it is the most popular operation in the UK with women increasingly asking for it themselves.⁹ It is thus likely that feminists exaggerate the dangers of the operation. As Dr. Kalakoutis states: 'Yes there is a risk in a [c]aesarean [s]ection, just like there is a risk in a normal delivery and just like there is risk in a nail removal operation.'¹⁰ Moreover, one could argue that a caesarean section does not compromise the woman's autonomy since she considered these risks and consented to them when she decided not to have an abortion: she made an informed choice in keeping the baby and that included the chance of having to go through the operation to bring the baby safe into the world. 16% of pregnant women who give birth in the UK have a

⁴ [1998] 3 WLR 936.

⁵ [1997] 2 FLR 426.

⁶ D Sperling *Management of Post-Mortem Pregnancy, Legal and Philosophical Aspects* (Ashgate Publishing Hampshire 2006) 20.

⁷ Interview with Gabriel M Kalakoutis, Gynaecologist and Consultant at Aretaeio Hospital (Nicosia Cyprus 2 January 2009).

⁸ W Savage 'Caesarean section: Who Chooses – The Woman Or Her Doctor?' in D Dickenson (ed) *Ethical Issues in Maternal – Foetal Medicine* (Cambridge University Press Cambridge 2002) 264.

⁹ *ibid* 265.

¹⁰ Kalakoutis (n 7).

caesarean section and she could well have been one of them.¹¹ Therefore, the self-determination argument fails to capture the whole picture as ‘a unique situation: a situation where there is a particular need to examine what is meant by autonomous choice, given that the woman has made a decision to continue with the pregnancy.’¹² The traditional understanding of autonomy, as the ‘trump card beating all the other principles,’¹³ creates an all or nothing approach and in an attempt to completely protect the woman’s rights, it completely ignores not only the foetal rights that are at stake, but society’s duty to protect human life in general.

Sperling¹⁴ mentions the possibility of a woman who did not impliedly consent to caesarean section because she never really had a chance to have an abortion. She might have kept the foetus not as a result of a deliberate choice but because of lack of access to therapeutic abortion, cultural, social, familial and personal constraints. With due respect, this author finds this argument insulting to all the women who have a legitimate reason for denying a caesarean section: if Sperling’s argument was accepted, it would lead to a double tragedy. Just because the woman was unfortunate enough to be forced to go through a pregnancy, that does not give her the right to kill the foetus at a later, in fact the latest, stage. Two wrongs simply do not make a right and if she does not want the foetus, she can give it up for adoption, not kill it by claiming that she has a right to do so by appealing to her self-determination as a human being.

Dworkin gives a useful example of the interaction between paternalism and autonomous decisions.¹⁵ Ancient Greek mythology said that when Odysseus was passing by the island of the Sirens, he ordered his men to tie him to a pole and ignore all his later orders to approach the island until they could no longer hear the Sirens’ song. This is because their song would lure him onto the island, where he would face definite death. It could be argued that even if he had not given such an order, the sailors would be justified in acting paternalistically and ignoring his orders because they would be protecting his life, thus ensuring his long term autonomy. After all, ‘autonomy is of no value to a dead person.’¹⁶ Although this is a good example where paternalism and autonomy align, it cannot be equated with the pregnant woman scenario. It can be assumed that long term survival was part of Odysseus’ plan but in the case of the pregnant woman, the exercise of paternalism could result in a quality of life that the woman considers insufficient in reflecting a satisfactory understanding of herself.¹⁷ Arguably, survival is not worth much if you do not have something worth surviving for.

2 The Discrimination Argument

The autonomy argument is supported by feminists who argue that pregnant women, like every other human being, have a right to control their body and that forcing them to go through the operation, is discriminatory.¹⁸ However, the discrimination argument is flawed in that it ignores the fact that the pregnant woman is treated differently precisely because she

¹¹ Sperling (n 6) 265.

¹² *ibid.*

¹³ M Brazier ‘Do No Harm – Do Patients Have Responsibilities Too?’ (2006) *Cambridge Law Journal* 65(2) 397, 400.

¹⁴ Sperling (n 6) 21.

¹⁵ G Dworkin *The Theory and Practice of Autonomy* (Cambridge University Press Cambridge 1988) 14.

¹⁶ S Glick ‘The Morality of Coercion’ (2000) 26 *Journal of Medical Ethics* 393.

¹⁷ M Stauch ‘Court Authorised Caesarean Sections and the Principle of Patient Autonomy: Re MB (an Adult: Medical Treatment)’ (1997) 6 *Nottingham Law Review* 74.

¹⁸ R Roth *Making Women Pay : The Hidden Costs of Foetal Rights* (Cornell University Press Cornell 2000).

is different from everyone else. She carries a viable human being inside her and she has the moral, if not legal obligation to protect it.

The classic feminist argument is that the law does not oblige a father to go through a kidney transplant operation to save his child and neither should it oblige a woman to go through an equally dangerous operation to deliver a foetus that is not even considered an entity under the law.¹⁹ However, this is not a question of legal obligations but of moral ones. The question that should be asked is: is a father morally obliged to give a kidney to save his child's life? This depends on a number of factors: what are the risks of the operation, is there anyone else to take care of his other children and bring money to the family while he is recovering from the operation, what are the chances of the operation succeeding etc. Only he can assess the advantages and disadvantages of such a decision because it reflects his understanding of life as a human being and when he does, his decision is respected. One wonders why a pregnant woman is to be treated differently. One could argue that the pregnant woman and the father are not like situations. A father is not obliged to go through the operation because he might have conflicting moral obligations and only he can decide between them. A pregnant woman on the other hand, should have a legal obligation to deliver the child because her reasons for not wanting to go through with the operation are purely selfish: she is allowing her child to die because she is afraid of needles,²⁰ because she believes that a blood transfusion would compromise her religion²¹ or because she believes in nature taking its course.²² However, the picture is not always black and white: is the woman who refuses to have a caesarean section because she will return to Nigeria where the necessary equipment for a possible second caesarean section²³ will not be available being selfish, or merely exercising the right given by her very existence, to reproduce? The argument of culpability being based on selfishness is unpersuasive because the pregnant woman, like the father in this example, has to balance conflicting moral obligations. After all, arguably the sacrifice of a child to prove one's devotion to God²⁴ is anything but selfish. Since there are situations where the pregnant woman will have to balance conflicting moral interests as well, she should be given a chance to do so and her choice should be respected.

It has been argued that the biggest danger in treating women differently from anyone else is fear of the slippery slope:²⁵ once women are denied the right to refuse treatment at delivery, there are logically no lengths to which doctors and courts can go to protect human life. However, the caesarean section scenario does not include a slippery slope danger at all. We are already at the bottom of the slope and the law can demand no more.²⁶ This is not necessarily a bad thing; after all, strict liability is not a foreign idea in the Anglo-American legal system. Sperling²⁷ argues that the standard of reasonable care is the only relevant standard in the parent-child relationship and is a constant one. Since it is not a standard of perfection, it cannot demand from a pregnant woman to risk her life for her baby. However,

¹⁹ *ibid.*

²⁰ *Re MB (An Adult: Medical Treatment)* [1997] 2 FLR 426.

²¹ *Re S (Adult: Refusal of Treatment)* [1992] 4 All ER 671.

²² *Re S (Hospital Patient: Court's jurisdiction)* [1996] Fam 123.

²³ These were the facts of *Re S (Adult Refusal of Treatment)* [1997] 2 FCR 541 CA. Medical evidence presented to Court stated that it is likely that if the woman has a caesarean section in her first birth, she will need a caesarean section for all her other births as well.

²⁴ For example, in the case of a Jehovah's Witness refusing a caesarean section.

²⁵ R Roth 'At Women's Expense: The Cost Of Foetal Rights' in J Merrick and R Blank (eds) *The Politics of Pregnancy: Policy Dilemmas in the Maternal-Foetal Relationship* (Kluwer Academic Publishers Netherlands 1993).

²⁶ Strictly speaking this is not true; policing of pregnancy during the whole nine months can arguably be at least as intrusive. A detailed discussion of this follows in the second part of the paper.

²⁷ Sperling (n 6).

logically this argument must be wrong. The parent's obligation towards the child is affected by the child's dependency on the parent. The parent might be able to leave a child to play in the park alone when he is 12, but not when he is two; similarly, he might not have an obligation to hold his 15 year-old son by the hand in a busy place but he has the obligation to do so if the son is severely disabled or blind. One's responsibility is relative to the other's dependency. If one accepts the argument that the foetus is the most vulnerable type of a child (albeit morally if not legally), then caesarean section cannot be rejected on a slippery slope argument: since the foetus is at its most vulnerable state, the mother cannot be asked to do anything more than what she is being asked to do now.

3 The Foetus and the Law

A foetus is not considered a legal entity under the law, thus it does not possess any legal rights. However, this does not preclude the possibility of the foetus being owed some moral rights because it was given a moral personality by the pregnant woman when she decided to carry on with the pregnancy. This counter-argument to autonomy is supported by a number of judicial statements. Lord Justice Judge in *St George's NHS Trust v S*²⁸ made this point clearly when he said that 'what else it may be, a 36 week foetus is not nothing: if viable it is not lifeless and is certainly human.'²⁹ The most obvious example of the law recognising some rights in the foetus is the prohibition of abortion in the majority of cases after the 24th week of pregnancy.³⁰ This is precisely because around the 24th week the foetus becomes viable and society feels that it must protect the right to life of a future human being. If the law is willing to trump the mother's autonomous decision in the context of abortion to protect the foetus (unless her health is at risk or there is a significant risk that the foetus will be severely handicapped), then it is at least arguable that it has the same right in the case of a forced caesarean section. Additionally, if policy arguments can be used to vitiate a freely given consent where harm is likely to occur,³¹ then one should at least consider the possibility that society can sidestep the woman's non-consent on the same grounds.³² These arguments are even stronger if we consider that we are not only protecting the moral interests of the foetus but the future legal interests of the person that this foetus will become. As Dr. Kalakoutis³³ argues, '[i]sn't it the same as injuring someone in order to prevent him from murdering a third person? My conscience is clean.'³⁴ Dr. Kalakoutis's reaction reflects the argument that as technology progresses, so should our understanding of morality. When the foetus is removed from the 'secrecy of the womb'³⁵ through ultrasound, it not only acquires social recognition, but it also enhances the doctor's perception that he is dealing with a second patient. It will thus be my position throughout this essay that despite the fact that the foetus' rights cannot always trump the rights of the mother, similarly it cannot be argued that the mother can decide what she will do without consideration towards the foetus simply on the basis of autonomy.

²⁸ [1998] 3 WLR 936.

²⁹ *ibid* 952.

³⁰ Abortion Act 1967 s 1(1), as amended by the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act 1990.

³¹ *R v Brown* [1993] 2 All ER 75.

³² A Maclean 'Caesarean Sections, Competence and the Illusion of Autonomy' (1999) 1 Web Journal of Current Legal Issues 4.

³³ Kalakoutis (n 7).

³⁴ *ibid*.

³⁵ R Blank 'Maternal Fetal Relationship: The Courts and Social Policy' in S Shirwan and B Parish (eds) *Women, Medicine, Ethics and the Law* (Dartmouth Publishing Dartmouth 2002) 129.

4 The Pregnant Woman's Perspective

The third argument frequently presented by feminists, is that a pregnant woman knows better than her doctors; the intimate relationship she has developed with the foetus simply points to the fact that a natural delivery would be the best way to go about things.³⁶ Sperling also argues that as a consequence of a forced caesarean section, the mother's relationship with her future baby might be compromised because the baby 'made' her do something she did not want to or because it did not rise up to the expectation of the natural delivery she wanted to have.³⁷ However, both of these arguments are unpersuasive. Most of us would blame a doctor for forcing a woman to have a mastectomy when he knows full well that she can have chemotherapy instead, because it is a very personal decision that only impacts on her body. But with the risk of sounding paternalistic, this is one of the situations where the doctor truly knows best – if the umbilical cord is tied around the foetus' neck or if the foetus is not in the right position in order to be delivered naturally, it is a question of fact and not of gut feeling. As for the argument that the mother will be disappointed by her baby, this again cannot stand. Parents sometimes expect things that their children simply cannot deliver: it's wrong for a mother's relationship with her child to be negatively influenced because the child is not as good an athlete as she wanted him to be; and it's preposterous to argue that a mother is negatively predisposed against her child because as a baby it cried more than she expected. Why is the mode of delivery any less absurd of an example?

Perhaps the most powerful argument against caesarean section is the consequentialist argument. The phrase 'forced caesarean section' has been repeated so many times, that it no longer makes an impact, yet its effects are profound. The woman will presumably be protesting strongly before the delivery and after it she will need time to recover from an operation that not only injured her physically but also psychologically. It is important to bear in mind what this process does to the woman's trust towards the medical profession. It is thus likely that the next time she becomes pregnant; she will prefer to deliver the baby at home, putting hers and the foetus' life at risk.³⁸ It is perhaps easy to exaggerate this argument: Dr Savage, in her 35 years as a doctor, only saw two cases in which the woman absolutely refused caesarean section.³⁹ Similarly, Dr. Kalakoutis in his 30 years of experience in Cyprus only saw one such case. However, these numerically limited cases are likely to be overexploited by the press, giving the impression that this is a frequent phenomenon, thus frightening women away from hospitals. Dr. Savage gives an example of the dangers inherent in such paternalist attitudes: the patient was a 16 year-old woman who did not speak English and her husband (a devout Muslim) would not consent to a caesarean section. When it became apparent that she could not deliver the baby naturally he agreed to the operation but by that time the baby had died because it could not come out of her unusually small pelvis. In the following years she delivered six healthy babies with caesarean section. Dr. Savage concludes: 'If we had gone to court, would he have tried to have his wife deliver at home the next time and perhaps die from a ruptured uterus? An unanswerable question.'⁴⁰ If he did, not only would the doctors have indirectly compromised her life, but the life of every other pregnant woman in a similar situation who read the story.

³⁶ Re AC 573 A2d 1235 (1990). This was one of the very first cases in the USA where a forced caesarean section was ordered; it made the news and became known as the 'Angela Carter' case.

³⁷ Sperling (n 6) 24.

³⁸ Kalakoutis (n 7).

³⁹ *ibid.*

⁴⁰ Kalakoutis (n 7) 279.

Therefore, even if one has the foetus's best interests in mind rather than the mother's, a forced caesarean section is simply not the answer.

5 What Direction Should the Law Take?

As illustrated above, at the centre of all these arguments lie two conflicting interests: the interest of the foetus to live and the interest of the mother to exercise her fundamental right as a human being and determine her actions. The law today (at least in theory) sees autonomy as the principle that should always prevail. However, 'the current emphasis upon the need to uphold autonomy is as dangerous as the previous emphasis upon the value of the unborn child.'⁴¹ This is because no principle can always be supreme over the other; a more subtle test balancing the two principles is appropriate.

Both sides have equally strong ethical arguments but medical ethics have to be applied in real world situations. Initially the argument whether a foetus lives or dies should depend on the mother's reasons sounds appealing. However, it must be rejected both on ethical and on practical grounds. If the test tries to determine whether the mother is being selfish, as was suggested in the kidney transplant example, her right of autonomy is completely ignored: autonomy is after all worth nothing if it is only exercised when it is compatible with the doctor's, the judge's or the majority's opinion. On more practical grounds, this criterion is problematic because it simply cannot be applied fairly. Most women only find out that they must go through a caesarean section after the contractions have started, when they are already exhausted from the long hours and the pain. A decision will have to be taken quickly, sometimes over the phone, even more frequently with the woman's opinion not even being heard because she does not have a lawyer.⁴² In cases where the woman's voice cannot be heard, the doctors are likely to give false or misleading information, leading the judge to decide in favour of the forced operation. For example, *St George's NHS Trust v S*⁴³ was heard during the lunch break and the court was falsely told that the woman was in labour for 24 hours and that 'every minute counted,'⁴⁴ This trend is reflected in the fact that 86% of the cases that have been heard by a judge resulted in a caesarean section.⁴⁵ Dr. Kalakoutis's statement when asked what he would do when a woman did not consent to the operation was clear: 'I would go ahead with it, since I would be protected by a court order.'⁴⁶ He did not even assume that the court might decide the other way and this is possibly because the court will only hear the one side of the story.⁴⁷

The vast majority of women consent to caesarean section. Those who do not, presumably do so because they feel strongly about the whole procedure. Some are justified, others are not. It is easy when you have all the time in the world to decide that the needle phobia patient should have the operation because it protects her long term autonomy but the Nigerian woman should not. Unfortunately, in such situations, time is not always available. If we allow doctors to invade a woman's body when they feel they must, they will do so even though the baby might be born unharmed by natural delivery as well. If we only allow women to decide, then there will be deaths that could be prevented. None of the two

⁴¹ Dworkin (n 14) 300.

⁴² Savage (n 8). In 5 out of 7 cases where a court order was obtained the woman was not represented by a barrister or a solicitor so her side was not heard.

⁴³ [1998] 3 WLR 936.

⁴⁴ *ibid* 947.

⁴⁵ V Kolder, J Gallagher and MT Parsons 'Court Ordered Obstetrical Interventions' (1987) *The New England Journal of Medicine* 316, 29-54.

⁴⁶ Kalakoutis (n 7).

⁴⁷ This is so even though doctors in Cyprus follow the English guidelines on such issues.

solutions will prevent tragedies 100%, but by having all the ethical and practical considerations in mind, it is safer to let the woman decide. This author is in agreement with Herring⁴⁸ that few pregnant women take a decision without taking into account the interests of the foetus. However, objections can be raised to the solution he proposes: to ask what the ordinary woman would want. Surely, this cannot be the solution. If we were dealing with ‘ordinary women,’ we would not be in this dilemma because the majority of them are very much willing to go through the operation to deliver a healthy child. Therefore, such a test would completely ignore the woman’s wishes as it would always find against her.

As Lord Justice Thorpe⁴⁹ pointed out: ‘[i]t is perhaps easier for an appellate court to discern principle than it is for a trial court to apply it in the face of judicial instinct, training and emotion.’⁵⁰ This is apparent in another context as well: while the majority of scholars reach the conclusion that the woman’s autonomy should be protected, the majority of the courts dealing with hard facts reach the opposite conclusion. It is much easier to talk of high values such as autonomy and self-determination when you know that what you say will not cost a human life. The problem with accepting that courts are at least excused in wanting to protect the foetus’s life when faced with the opportunity is that there is a pattern in the cases where caesarean section is forced: Janet Gallagher quotes a survey: 81% of the women subjected to court orders in the US were black, Asian or Hispanic, 44% were unmarried, 24% did not speak English as their primary language and none was a private patient.⁵¹ This is because these women are less capable of conveying the reasoning of their decisions because of language barriers and cultural discrimination. If the courts are to be given an opportunity to interfere, the test used must ensure that this is done fairly.

The proposed test therefore is to allow the woman to have the first and more influential say in this. This is not because her autonomy is the paramount principle; on the contrary, it is because she is the person who has created the strongest bond with the foetus. It is thus much more likely that the woman will have balanced all the factors and reached a better conclusion on what to do in such a difficult situation than a judge who has considered the matter for 20 minutes and does not have all the facts in front of him. This test does not imply that the woman’s opinion will always prevail because we must not exclude the possibility that she truly does not have the capacity to decide whether to go through with the operation. An example of that is *Norfolk and Norwich Healthcare NHS Trust v W*.⁵² The woman in this case was admitted to the hospital in a state of arrested labour but was denying the fact that she was pregnant. The judge in this case correctly decided that she was not in a position to decide whether she could have the operation. Nevertheless, in the majority of cases, the woman will be competent, will have thought of the implications of her decision in advance and her decision and justifications will have to be respected. This means that the competence test will have to be applied to her just like it would be applied to any other person, with one modification. The woman should not be able to refuse treatment for no reason at all⁵³ because that would suggest that she has not carried out the balancing exercise this suggestion requires. However, if the woman provides a reason, that reason should be respected. This would mean that some foetuses might die for reasons that the majority does not understand and does not agree with. At the same time, the relationship between the

⁴⁸ J Herring ‘Reproductive Technology and the Law: The Caesarean Section Cases and the Supremacy of Autonomy’ 2000 3 Law and Medicine Current Legal Issues.

⁴⁹ ‘A Woman’s Freedom from Attack’ The Times (8 July 1997).

⁵⁰ *ibid*.

⁵¹ J Gallagher ‘Foetus as Patient’ in S Cohen and N Taub (eds) *Reproductive Laws for the 1990s* (Humana Press 1989) 203.

⁵² [1996] 2 FCR 613.

⁵³ *Re T* [1993] Fam 95, 102 (Lord Donaldson).

doctor and the woman must also be one of trust and not only of protection: the doctor must trust that the woman took her decision responsibly, balancing not only the advantages for her but her future child as well. Surely, no one can do this better than her.

C THE POLICING OF WOMEN DURING PREGNANCY DEBATE

1 Arguments For and Against a Tougher Approach

Having decided that one cannot morally or legally impose an obligation on a woman to have a caesarean section simply because she is pregnant, one needs to discuss whether she has any obligations during the nine months of the pregnancy itself. The court in *St George's NHS Trust v S*⁵⁴ stated that 'while pregnancy increases the personal responsibilities of a woman, it does not diminish her entitlement to decide whether or not to undergo medical treatment.'⁵⁵ If one agrees with the second part of the statement, it is not entirely clear what is meant by the first. What added 'personal responsibilities' exist in the case of a pregnant woman? In a number of jurisdictions, courts have found third parties liable for harm done (even to non-viable) fetuses.⁵⁶ It is thus at least arguable that the same responsibility should exist for the primary carer of the foetus, the pregnant woman herself. However, this is a question where ethics should determine the law and not the other way round. Thus, the question should not be what the courts will decide, but what they should decide. Finally, one should consider, if the woman has legally enforceable obligations during the gestation period, what sanctions should attach on them?

By 'personal responsibilities' one can mean any number of obligations: some doctors believe that daily walking and listening to classical music helps the foetus develop into a healthier baby,⁵⁷ smoking and drinking alcohol are not illegal activities but they are strongly recommended against by doctors⁵⁸ and drug abuse is both illegal and destructive for the foetus's health.⁵⁹ Therefore, should pregnant women be policed in their actions and if so, where do we draw the line? This essay will only deal with the most difficult issue: is a pregnant woman who is addicted to drugs morally culpable and/or legally punishable for the death or serious injury of her child?

In most cases, the critical period of the foetus's development is between the third and the twelfth week of the pregnancy but some organs, including the brain, develop throughout the nine months.⁶⁰ One could argue that even though the infringement on the woman's privacy in this case is much more prolonged than in the forced caesarean section situation, her autonomy is not violated to the same extent. Justification for that is derived from Dworkin's Odysseus example mentioned in the first section: in that case, paternalism and Odysseus' long term autonomy were aligned. Similarly, in this case, it is in the best interest of the woman to stop using drugs whether she is pregnant or not. The State already infringes an addict's autonomy by criminalising such behaviour; now the law simply becomes more restrictive because there is another life at stake. One should thus look at the policing of

⁵⁴ [1998] 3 WLR 936.

⁵⁵ *ibid* 957.

⁵⁶ *VO v France* (2005) 40 EHRR.

⁵⁷ J L Hopson 'Foetal Psychology' (1998) 31 (5) *Psychology Today* 44.

⁵⁸ S Higgins 'Smoking in Pregnancy' (2002) 14 *Current Opinion in Obstetrics and Gynaecology* 14.

⁵⁹ L Curet and C Andrew 'Drug Abuse during Pregnancy' (2002) 45 *Clinical Obstetrics and Gynaecology* 73.

⁶⁰ R Blank (n 33) 133.

pregnancy debate not in terms of conflict between the mother and the foetus, but in terms of shared interests and obligations owed by society to both of them.⁶¹

In a different context, Bonnie Steinbock⁶² argued that drink driving is always immoral because even though the alcoholic has no control over his desire for the substance, he has control on whether to drive a car. Here, it could be argued that a pregnant addict is not acting as immorally as the alcoholic driver. Unlike her husband who can leave the room to have a cigarette, or the alcoholic who can take a taxi, she cannot separate herself, thus her actions, from the foetus. That does not mean that by taking drugs she is not acting immorally, it merely suggests that not everyone is as culpable as our initial reactions would suggest. Bewley⁶³ suggests that the way to determine the culpability of the woman is to balance what she is sacrificing against what harm she is preventing. She gives the example of soft cheese: doctors believe that some soft cheese has adverse effects on the embryo. She thus argues that a woman who fails to stop eating gorgonzola is much more morally culpable than a woman who cannot get off her heroin addiction. Although this is persuasive on the facts of the example, it can lead to problematic conclusions since it suggests that the same effort is required from each individual to stop using drugs. In reality, two women who have been taking the same drug for the same time will not behave in the same way during rehabilitation because drug taking is largely connected with psychological and not only physical factors.⁶⁴ Therefore, such a test for culpability would lead to the unfair situation of putting addict women in groups of more and less blameworthy people depending on their emotional status at the time.

The argument in favour of policing pregnancy is that the woman has impliedly agreed that she would deliver the foetus not only alive, but to the best of her powers, healthy. As the court put it in *Smith v Brennan*, 'a child has a legal right to begin life with a sound mind and body'.⁶⁵ She therefore has a moral obligation as a mother to stop possible harmful actions. Coupled with that, is the argument that the same obligation is imposed on her by society which has an interest in protecting its children and ensuring that they will suffer from the minimum possible harm. The fact that the pregnant woman has already gone through enormous sacrifices for the foetus should not matter; taking drugs is one of the factors that makes her automatically morally liable for harming the foetus.

Having mentioned society's obligations towards the foetus however, one should not forget that it also has obligations towards the woman. These include an obligation to protect women's rights, rights that have only been recognised in the last part of the twentieth century and are still not well cemented. Feminists are thus justifiably worried that policing pregnancy will take us back to the days when 'enslavement of women was justified as biological destiny.'⁶⁶ If we can force women to stop taking drugs or smoking on policy grounds, then an employer who fires a pregnant woman from a more risky working environment on grounds of protecting the foetus might have an arguable case. Following from that, it is not difficult to imagine a situation whereby women of child bearing age (which is most of their life) are stopped from working in more dangerous environments. This becomes even more discriminatory because studies show that long term exposure of a man to hazardous conditions does not make him infertile as was originally thought, but can affect the

⁶¹ *ibid* 138.

⁶² B Steinbock 'Drunk Driving' (1985) 14 *Philosophy and Public Affairs* 278-95.

⁶³ S Bewley 'Restricting the Freedom of Pregnant Women' in D Dickenson (ed) *Ethical Issues in Maternal – Foetal Medicine* (Cambridge University Press Cambridge 2002) 141.

⁶⁴ S Jones and P Heaven 'Psychosocial Correlates of Adolescent Drug-Taking Behaviour' (1998) 21 *Journal of Adolescence* 127, 134.

⁶⁵ (1960) Ad 2497, 503.

⁶⁶ Bewley (n 60) 130.

quality of his sperm.⁶⁷ Clearly a woman is more connected to the foetus than the man, but both contribute to its health condition. Where is the line between protecting the foetus and discriminating against the woman drawn?

2 What are the Possible Approaches the Law Could Take?

A right means nothing if it cannot be enforced. If the foetus has such a right, what actions will the future child or society itself be able to take against the woman? There are a number of options, but arguably the most effective punishment or deterrent will be the woman's knowledge that she is hurting her child. One should therefore consider whether the threat of going to prison for manslaughter could convince a woman to stop taking drugs. There are already criminal sanctions against drug-taking but they have proven ineffective as deterrents. After all, anyone who understands the situation in which a heroin addict is found, must know that the woman does not really 'want' to take the drugs, she 'needs' to. She wants to save her child but her need for heroin might be stronger. Similarly then, she might want to avoid imprisonment, but that will not stop her from desiring the drug. In the words of Bewley, 'a woman who cannot give up drugs despite her best intent does not have a free will. This is a double tragedy, as she harms her foetus against her will, and her will is not free and autonomous.'⁶⁸

Moreover, it is questionable whether the threat of imprisonment hanging over the head of a pregnant woman will have the desired effects. It is more likely to make her worried and lead her to drugs once more for consolation. Also, if it becomes known that pregnant addicts are prosecuted and imprisoned, women are more likely to avoid seeing the doctor in the first place. This means not only that they will give birth at home without the help of an expert, but also that the development of the foetus during the nine months will not be monitored.⁶⁹ Problematically, it is these vulnerable foetuses that need the most attention. Thus, if our main aim is to protect the foetus rather than punish the woman, criminalising her cannot be the solution. Nevertheless, it should not be excluded as an option. It should be used as a last resort where there is evidence that the mother was offered adequate care for her condition, yet she refused to use it accordingly.

Criminalising pregnant addicts is not only theoretically difficult to justify, but also creates practical considerations in its application. Roth argues that a study of women in Florida including private and public hospitals found that alcohol and drug abuse are common amongst women regardless of their race and socioeconomic status.⁷⁰ Despite this, black women are nearly ten times more likely to be reported than white women and nearly all women who were reported were of low socioeconomic status.⁷¹ Therefore, women in minorities and of low socioeconomic status are more likely to be targeted, convicted and further harmed in prison, creating a vicious circle of drug problems and troubled families in specific sectors of society. A child whose mother is in prison or has been released but is still addicted to heroin is more likely to be raised more poorly than a child in a normal family unit. Sentencing therefore is not only harming pregnant women, but their babies as well, the very people who we were trying to protect in the first place. A study for pregnancy and

⁶⁷ C R Daniels 'Between Fathers and Foetuses: The Social Construction of Male Reproduction and the Politics of Foetal Harm' in D Dickenson (ed) *Ethical Issues in Maternal – Foetal Medicine* (Cambridge University Press Cambridge 2002) 241.

⁶⁸ Bewley (n 60) 126.

⁶⁹ Savage (n 8) 279.

⁷⁰ R Roth (n 24) 126.

⁷¹ *ibid.*

alcohol use showed that women who consumed three drinks a day but ate a balanced diet, had a foetal alcohol syndrome of 4.5% while those who drank the same amount but were malnourished had a foetal alcohol syndrome rate of 71%.⁷² Daniels therefore persuasively argues that since malnutrition ties directly to income, 'Foetal alcohol syndrome is a measure not only of maternal alcoholism but also of economic class.'⁷³ Clearly, punishing the woman rather than providing help for her, except in the most exceptional circumstances, cannot be in her best interests, her baby's, or society's.

A second type of remedy could be a civil action whereby the child would be able to claim compensation for injuries induced during the gestation period due to the mother's drug taking habits. An action in tort will have the advantage of the court deciding whether it is 'fair, just and reasonable'⁷⁴ to award damages. This will again depend on the efforts put by the woman to stop taking drugs and whether they were genuine or not. On the other hand, an action for damages is unlikely to be very effective since a drug addict rarely has money to pay for a potential law suit. Additionally, this action will not have protected the foetus although, if the mother pays, it is likely that it will make the child's life easier in terms of potential medical treatment he is likely to need due to the injuries induced. Therefore, such an option should be available to the child although it is appreciated that it will only be effective in exceptional circumstances.

The final remedy would be to take the child away from the mother immediately after birth. Even though this cannot prevent the original harm from happening, it will avoid any further harm. However, the baby should not be automatically taken away from the mother simply because she was using drugs during pregnancy. This should only be done in cases where the baby is still in danger because the parent is still using drugs. This is a frustratingly inadequate response: it is recognised that there will be cases in which children will be left in the hands of parents who might go back to their drug-taking habits. However, the alternative would be to prevent a woman who has stopped using drugs for the sake of her child from raising it. The possibility of forcing a woman to stop taking drugs will not be discussed in detail since no one can force an addict off such a habit unless the addict herself wants to. If she does not want to stop taking the drugs herself, she will return back to her old habits as soon as she leaves the rehabilitation centre and the State will have wasted money that could have been used on a more willing woman instead.

3 The Middle Solution

It seems therefore, that the only adequate way to protect a foetus is through the education and awareness-raising of its environment. If society can punish a woman because it has an interest to protect the foetus, then some self-criticism is also necessary due to its failure to act proactively to protect this interest. It needs to provide proper nutrition, counselling, substance abuse and mental health services and more generally adequate health care. It is of course much easier to blame someone else altogether rather than take partial responsibility for a problematic situation. Sending a woman to prison is easier to implement than proactively providing the necessary help for her. However, in the long run, such tactics will work for the best interest of society. If incentives are given to addicts to come forward rather than having to spend resources to track them down, prosecute and put them to prison, society will not only be gaining the invaluable intangible benefits of prevention of a death, but economic advantages as well. The Institute of Medicine in the USA concluded that for each

⁷² Daniels (n 64) 117.

⁷³ *ibid.*

⁷⁴ *Caparo Industries Plc v Dickman* [1990] 2 AC (HL) 605.

dollar spent on prenatal care, \$3.38 was being saved.⁷⁵ Furthermore, arguments from both sides make it appear that this is an either/or debate: either the mother's autonomy is protected or the foetus's right to life. Unlike the caesarean section debate, this is not the case here. Encouraging women to come forward on their own is the most appropriate middle solution.

Evidence suggests that even when prenatal care is available, many high risk pregnant women avoid it.⁷⁶ This derives partly from the fact that a number of drug addicts feel rejected by society and are therefore less likely to trust the authorities. Another part of the problem is that many women do not realise the extent to which they are hurting the foetus and that something can be done to stop this. It is thus important that awareness-raising campaigns take place and that the State carries out the appropriate marketing to attract estranged women. Daniels⁷⁷ criticises the US government for presenting discriminatory advertisements because public health care warnings are often produced in Spanish, typically show African-American and Latina women and are directed at inner-city neighbourhoods. However, arguably this is not discriminatory, just an effective way of targeting the most appropriate audience. It is submitted that these minorities, especially the women, are less likely to be aware of the advantages of appropriate healthcare due to language barriers and because they do not have easy access to such information. Inner-city neighbourhoods are where the majority of such high risk pregnant women live. A poster's aim is to make an immediate impression on the person whom it tries to affect; that includes the person being able to identify with the picture and understanding the words. At a time when conservative estimations show 41,000 'crack babies' a year⁷⁸ being born in the US alone, such criticisms are deflecting our attention from the main issue of saving lives.

However, one criticism can be successfully be made about such awareness raising campaigns: they exclusively target women. This discussion has so far only dealt with the policing of pregnant women, but one should not forget that a pregnant woman does not live in isolation from the rest of the world. One New Jersey public health advertisement showed a pregnant woman holding a drink and warned that 'A pregnant woman never drinks alone'. As Daniels points out however, 'a pregnant woman also never drinks in isolation from the effects of her home, her physical, social and political environment.'⁷⁹ Society cannot expect pregnant women to quit smoking when it does not warn future fathers that their child could be facing health problems due to the fact that their wife is a passive smoker during her pregnancy. Similarly, it is unfair and discriminatory to talk of foetuses being 'exposed to illicit drugs in the womb'⁸⁰ when no one attributes fault to the male partner who could be using drugs for years. This attitude is partly due to the fact that for many years it was believed that if a man damaged his sperm by taking drugs he simply became infertile. This is no longer the case.⁸¹ As our understanding of foetal development progresses so should our responses towards it. If society is willing to police pregnant women on the grounds of public policy, it should at least make men aware that they have roles and responsibilities before the baby is born as well.⁸²

⁷⁵ n 33, 131.

⁷⁶ *ibid* 141.

⁷⁷ Daniels (n 64).

⁷⁸ Daniels (n 64) 115.

⁷⁹ *ibid* 117.

⁸⁰ *ibid* 115.

⁸¹ *ibid* 141.

⁸² H Draper 'Women, Forced Caesareans and Antenatal Responsibilities' (1996) 22 *Journal of Medical Ethics* 327.

D CONCLUSION

Ethical considerations are very important in the policing of pregnant women debate both during and at the very end of the gestation period. However, practical considerations are what make the difference. Pregnant women are treated differently not because they are less human than everyone else, but because they choose to carry out the greatest gift their human nature has given them. High values such as autonomy, right to life, self-determination, privacy, come down to one thing: saving lives. A life however is not only destroyed when one stops breathing; it is also destroyed when she feels she has sacrificed her religion for the sake of her child or when she has sacrificed her child for the sake of drugs. Thus, a woman should be able to decide whether to go through with the caesarean section or not as long as she makes it clear that she has thought of the consequences of her decision for her and her foetus. Only if this test is not satisfied should society be permitted to intervene. Similarly, if the woman is an addict, she should be given the opportunity to ask for help and when she does, it should be made available; only then should more coercive measures be used. Society has an obligation to help its members; but it is often forgotten that pregnant women are as much members of our society as future babies. The only feasible way to strike a balance between society's two conflicting obligations is to give the woman the primary responsibility and only act in extreme situations. This of course will not always be 100% satisfactory, but no blanket rule either in favour of the mother or the child can achieve a better result.